

Adaptive Polarization for Spacecraft Communications Systems¹²

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Abstract—Communications antennas on spacecraft are usually circularly polarized. As the spacecraft maneuvers, its antenna and the ground station antenna may not point directly at each other. Antennas not properly aligned for optimal power transfer usually create a polarization mismatch and a loss in transferred power. In this paper, a scheme for compensating for polarization mismatch is considered using crossed dipoles. One of the crossed dipole's amplitude and phase is adjusted using numerical optimization, and the Numerical Electromagnetic Code generates the electromagnetic response. Optimizing only for circular polarization produces losses in radiated power that offset the polarization correction. The polarization optimization may improve power transferred when the spacing between the orthogonal dipoles is increased. The next step modified the optimization process to consider power transferred. With this improvement, the power transferred always increased up to a maximum of 2.0 dB at $\theta = 80^\circ$. Using adaptive crossed dipoles at the transmitter and receiver was also considered and further improved the model.

any direction. This correction will compensate for any error resulting from the antennas not having an accurate mechanical pointing system or being designed without a pointing system. These antenna misalignments result from the direction of propagation not corresponding to the antenna's designed direction for maximum gain and circular polarization. This paper describes a method for adaptively compensating for polarization loss in an antenna communications system.

To generate the desired transmit antenna pattern and circular polarization, a pair of crossed dipoles is positioned with one parallel to the x-axis and one parallel to the y-axis. A point source receiving antenna having circular polarization of the desired sense will be simulated to simplify the optimization. The separation distance between the transmit and receive dipoles and the presence of a ground plane were also briefly considered in various configurations to understand the ability of the optimization to correct for the depolarization of the electromagnetic wave in a particular direction. The optimization technique adjusts the amplitude and phase of one of the dipoles until the desired response is obtained.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The widespread use of satellites has increased the need to consider polarization when designing and constructing antennas. Satellite antennas use circular polarization to mitigate atmospheric losses in electromagnetic waves due to the Faraday rotation. This project focuses on the use of an optimization method to correct the polarization of an antenna system to transmit or receive maximum power in

In this paper, three models were optimized. The first approach forced the transmit dipoles to transmit a field that was as close to circular polarization as possible. Unfortunately, the loss in transmit gain offset the improved polarization match. The next approach optimized the transmit dipoles for maximum power transfer to a circularly polarized point source. Finally, transmit and receive crossed dipoles were optimized for maximum power transfer. The final configuration resulted in the best performance.

Previous work

Previous work investigating the polarization of radio waves dates back to the beginning of the 20th century, but research into adaptive systems using polarization appeared much later on. A paper published in 1974 by Marshall [1]

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described a method to correct for the polarization change caused by rain in a communication channel. The proposed system used variable elliptical polarization with properties dependent upon the rainfall rate. This approach was not computer controlled and only corrected the polarization for broadside transmission. The desired properties of the elliptically polarized wave were derived from equations describing the depolarization of the transmitted wave due to rainfall.

In 1981 Compton published work using crossed dipoles in an array that has application to receiving signals when there is an antenna misalignment [2]. His system consists of two pairs of crossed dipoles separated by some distance, but with the dipole elements are in the same plane. With this setup an LMS algorithm was used to optimize the array for a desired signal, and reject an interfering signal. Most of the work was done with the desired signal arriving perpendicular to the plane containing the pairs of crossed dipoles, but he does consider the case of the desired signal coming from an off-broadside direction. This misalignment of the desired signal is the focus of the current work, and Compton's treatment of this case shows that signal discrimination is possible. His method does require two sets of crossed dipoles, because the LMS algorithm needs the phase information provided by their physical separation to deal with misaligned signals. Compton's work is closest to the present work in his consideration of crossed dipoles and the ability to handle a directional misalignment of the desired signal.

Other work has been done in generating circular polarization from orthogonal sources, but the present project is unique in its consideration of circularly polarized antenna misalignment.

2. SIMULATION METHOD

MATLAB was used in conjunction with the Numerical Electromagnetics Code (NEC) to optimize and model the antenna. This process is summarized in the block diagram shown in Figure 1.

Communication Link Geometry

The geometry of the problem consists of a transmit antenna composed of crossed dipoles. Figure 2 shows the coordinate system with the optimization point specified in the far field by the angles θ and ϕ . The user sets the desired sense for the circular polarization (right-hand or left-hand). The initial amplitude and phase for the dipoles is based on generating the desired circular polarization broadside to the dipoles in the hemisphere containing the optimization point. The dipole separation also contributes to the polarization radiated by the antenna as shown in Figure 3. For the minimum separation case, the spacing is equal to doubling the wire radius plus an additional quarter wire radius.

Figure 1. Optimization flow chart.

Optimization Technique

There are several possible ways to optimize power transfer between the transmit and receive antennas. We selected a local search algorithm, Nelder Mead downhill simplex method, to perform the optimization. The optimization

Figure 2 - Location of the Optimization Point.

problem requires the magnitude and the phase of one dipole to be adjusted to achieve circular polarization at the chosen optimization point. This optimization may adjust the magnitude of the second dipole to values greater than one, but the important result is the ratio of the magnitudes between the two dipoles. The objective function inputs are the current magnitude and phase for the second dipole. With this input file, the NEC program itself is called and it

produces several output files containing the simulated results of the crossed dipoles [3]. MATLAB then extracts the inverse axial ratio, the tilt, and the sense from a special file created by modifying the NEC source code. Inverse axial ratio is the ratio of the polarization ellipse's semiminor axis divided by semimajor axis. It also extracts the relative power of the signal at the optimization point using another NEC file.

After the optimization finishes, MATLAB plots the resulting data. The plot in Figure 4 displays the starting inverse axial ratio and tilt at the optimization point and the final inverse axial ratio and sense. The plot also displays the optimized amplitude and phase driving the second dipole.

3. POLARIZATION OPTIMIZATION

The initial optimization focused on forcing the transmit pair of dipoles to produce a circularly polarized wave in the

specified direction. The simulation results are presented for several configurations of crossed dipoles, as the adaptive system's capabilities were explored.

Ideal Crossed Dipoles

First let us consider the ideal pair of crossed dipoles in the xy-plane. The antenna pattern for the dipole pair when configured to create circular polarization at $\theta = 0^\circ$ is shown in Figure 5, with the angles on the figures indicate the point of view for each pattern. Note these patterns are only for the top half of the radiation pattern. The heavy lines at the bottom represent the locations of the dipoles. NEC generates the inverse axial ratio of any point in the antenna pattern, and for this pair of dipoles the inverse axial ratio follows a cosine curve as θ varies from 0° to 90° . This result is shown in Figure 6 as a plot of the inverse axial ratio vs. θ . By using this information it is possible to determine the decrease in gain at a given angle.

Result: Y-Axis Dipole Driven with Magnitude = 0.70268 and Phase = 82.2752 (deg)

Figure 4. Three-dimensional optimization data display.

Figure 5 - Ideal Crossed Dipoles Antenna Pattern.

Figure 6 - Inverse Axial Ratio of Ideal Crossed Dipoles vs. Angle.

Figure 7. Polarization Mismatch Loss vs. Angle.

This polarization loss is shown in Figure 7 for different values of θ . In the simulated results the adaptation of the amplitude and phase of the y-axis dipole yields a circularly polarized wave in any direction up to a value of $\theta = 85^\circ$.

Non-Ideal Crossed Dipoles

Next let us consider a less ideal set of crossed dipoles, where the two are not co-located in the xy-plane, but they have some minimal vertical separation due to the thickness of the antenna and the need to maintain a physical separation. This separation was determined by using the radius of the wire for the antenna elements, and was equal to two times the radius of the wire plus another fourth of a wire's radius. With this configuration the optimizer determined that a magnitude of one and a phase of 88.6406° was required to produce circular polarization at $\theta = 0^\circ$. This is as expected as the spacing between the dipoles introduces a phase shift to the signal. The antenna pattern produced using this non-ideal set of crossed dipoles is shown in Figure 8 (the angles on the figure indicate the point of view for the figure). Note the slight change in the nulls of the pattern. By using this pattern as the baseline for optimization in other directions, it was once again

determined that circular polarization could be produced in any direction, and the resulting polarization gain follows closely that of the ideal crossed dipole case. The failure of this optimization setup occurs when the change in the antenna pattern is taken into account after the optimization has adjusted the magnitude and phase driving the second dipole. To produce the circular polarization at any point, the location of the nulls in the antenna pattern changes as the difference in the phase between the two dipoles changes.

Consider the case where the circular polarization is desired in the direction $\theta = 35^\circ$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$. The optimizer determines that a magnitude of 0.75257 and a phase of 89.0827° are required to achieve circular polarization. From these values, a gain of 0.09 dBi is achieved by correcting the polarization, but a radiated loss of -0.34 dBi occurs due to the change in the antenna pattern. Therefore the net gain due to optimization is -0.24 dB. The change in the antenna pattern is shown in Figure 9. Note the new placement of the nulls. Another example of this optimization failure is shown for a $\theta = 20^\circ$ and $\phi = 45^\circ$ optimization point. The placement of the null at $\phi = 45^\circ$ is clearly shown in Figure 10.

Figure 8 - Non-ideal Crossed Dipoles Antenna Pattern.

Figure 9 - Antenna Pattern after Optimization at $\theta = 35^\circ$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$.

Figure 10 - Antenna Pattern after Optimization at $\theta = 20^\circ$ and $\phi = 45^\circ$.

Non-Ideal Crossed Dipoles with a Ground Plane

To further examine the use of crossed dipoles, a ground plane was introduced into the problem with the non-ideal crossed dipoles. This configuration was used for spacing between the ground plane and the dipole pair of 0.25, 0.375, and 0.15 wavelengths. The addition of the ground plane creates a reflection of the crossed dipoles, and the optimizer was once again able to produce a circular polarized wave in all directions where $\theta < 85^\circ$. Each of these configurations yielded a larger gain in the direction perpendicular to the dipoles as expected for a reflected wave. All of these configurations suffer from the same gain problems as the single crossed dipoles, in that the optimization increases the gain due to the polarization match, but decreases the radiated power in the desired direction, resulting in a loss of total power.

Crossed Dipoles with Larger Separations

The one area where the polarization adaptation of the antennas produces an increase in gain relative to the starting pattern occurs when the spacing between the dipoles increases beyond 0.25 wavelength. Several simulations were conducted using larger separations and in some cases the polarization mismatch created a significant loss and the resulting optimization produced an increase in total power transferred by correcting for the mismatch. This adaptation would be applicable when the physical requirements of a system are such that the dipoles must have a larger separation, but still may be oriented as a crossed pair; otherwise a non-adaptive system seems to give better results.

4. TRANSFERRED POWER OPTIMIZATION

The previous section shows that optimizing the circular polarization of the transmit antenna is generally insufficient to increase the total transferred power in a communication system. In this section, the objective function was modified

to maximize the transferred power in the chosen direction.

Optimized Crossed Dipoles Transmitting to a Point Source

The communication system includes a pair of crossed dipoles with minimum separation and the isotropic receive antenna with circular polarization at the optimization point. In using this setup the MATLAB script was run for several receive points with the results shown in Table 1. The first optimization had $\theta = 0^\circ$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$ as the receive point, and it produced circular polarization, as shown by the final inverse axial ratio, in the direction perpendicular to the plane containing the crossed dipoles. After this first optimization the second dipole's magnitude and phase were used as a starting point for the remaining receive points considered.

In Table 1 the radiated power as calculated by the NEC is the power transferred between the dipoles and the optimization point without considering the polarization of the wave, or it is the power radiated in the chosen direction. The power transferred, in Table 1, is the radiation pattern power plus the polarization factor. It represents the gain in the link over an isotropic point source system, with the normalization resulting from the NEC's calculation of radiated power, and MATLAB's calculation of the polarization factor. The final column in Table 1 is the change in transferred power between the pre-optimized results, and the post-optimization results. This number indicates an increase in power due to the optimization. The data indicate that the power transferred increased in every case, and is due to a decrease in polarization efficiency and an increase in the power radiated in the chosen direction. To understand the gain resulting from the optimization Figure 11 shows a plot of the total gain vs. the angle θ . In this figure, the $\phi = 0^\circ$ and $\phi = 90^\circ$ curves are nearly identical and appear to be superimposed.

Table 1. Revised Optimizer Results for Minimum Dipole Spacing.

θ (deg)	ϕ (deg)	Initial Inverse Axial Ratio	Initial Radiated Power (dBi)	Initial Power Transferred (dBi)	Final Inverse Axial Ratio	Final Radiated Power (dBi)	Optimized Power Transferred (dBi)	Increase Resulting From Optimization (dB)
0	0	0.939	2.18	2.18	1.00	2.18	2.18	0.00
20	0	0.911	1.80	1.79	0.831	1.84	1.80	0.01
40	0	0.686	0.85	0.70	0.471	1.38	0.85	0.15
60	0	0.408	-0.16	-0.86	0.167	1.64	-0.16	0.70
80	0	0.133	-0.75	-2.75	0.018	2.11	-0.75	2.00
20	45	0.943	1.79	1.78	0.883	1.81	1.79	0.01
40	45	0.777	0.69	0.62	0.587	0.99	0.71	0.09
60	45	0.516	-0.80	-1.23	0.251	0.61	-0.72	0.51
80	45	0.183	-2.04	-3.73	0.030	0.94	-1.82	1.91
20	90	0.911	1.80	1.79	0.830	1.84	1.80	0.01
40	90	0.686	0.85	0.70	0.471	1.38	0.85	0.15
60	90	0.408	-0.16	-0.86	0.167	1.63	-0.16	0.70
80	90	0.133	-0.75	-2.75	0.017	2.11	-0.75	2.00

Figure 11 - Total Improvement in Gain using Transferred Power Optimization vs. Angle.

The greatest benefits from this optimization are as the angle θ increases or where the losses are initially the greatest. The antenna pattern for the receive point with the largest improvement is shown in Figure 12. The increase in gain after optimization occurs due to the movement of the nulls away from the direction of the optimization point. This movement of the nulls increases the radiation pattern power in the desired direction, and thus increases the total power transferred. At larger angles of θ the increase in power transferred is due to the larger loss in the radiation pattern at those angles in the initial condition. The increases are not without a loss in polarization efficiency, as the inverse axial

ratio always decreases. The data taken for crossed dipoles with minimum separation indicate that an increase in gain of up to 1.9 to 2.0 dB is possible depending on the receive point. This optimization for transferred power holds promise as an effective way to increase the gain. This increase could allow improvements in a communication system, as the simple adjustments to phase and magnitude are implemented.

Another possible use of this optimization would be with a more directive antenna such as a Yagi or a helix. Using a pair of Yagi antennas the polarization would be similar to

the crossed dipoles, but the antenna pattern is much more directive. This difference in the antenna pattern would also limit the ability of the optimizer to increase the power transferred in any direction of propagation due to a limited ability to change the power radiated in a particular direction. The helix antenna also has limitations when used with the developed optimization. It is also highly directive and not easily adjusted to increase the power radiated in different directions. Also, the geometry of the helix does not lend itself to polarization adjustment. Therefore, highly directive antennas may not lend themselves to optimization.

Crossed Dipoles as Transmit and Receive Antennas

To further test the optimizer's ability to increase the total power transferred in a communications link, two pairs of crossed dipoles were considered with one as the transmitter and one as the receiver. The initial power transferred between the two pairs of dipoles was determined when both produce circular polarization in the direction perpendicular to the dipoles. For the first set of simulations, the

transmitter pair of dipoles was optimized and the receive pair maintained its circular polarization.

By using the two pairs of crossed dipoles, it is possible to set up any direction of propagation relative to the transmit pair and the receive pair. Various directions of propagation were simulated with the results shown in Table 2. From these simulations the improvement over the previously considered point source receiver is evident, especially at the larger angles of θ . For example, at $\theta = 80^\circ$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$ the power transferred after optimization is 1.36 dBi where the previous result from Table 2 has a power transferred of -0.75 dBi. The greatest advantage of the two pairs of dipoles is found in the directivity of the second pair of dipoles and yields the increases in power transferred. In general, the optimization of just the transmitter pair of dipoles yields an increase in gain over the single pair optimization. It is also interesting to note that the optimization tends to turn off the dipole that is parallel to the direction of propagation for large angles of θ .

Figure 12 - Antenna pattern for $\theta = 80^\circ$ and $\phi = 0^\circ$ using transferred power optimization.

Table 2. Transferred Power Optimization for Two Pairs of Dipoles, One Pair Optimized.

Direction of Propagation Relative to the Transmit Pair		Direction of Propagation Relative to the Receive Pair		Power Transferred		Transmit Pair Final Parameters			Receive Pair Final Parameters		
θ (deg)	ϕ (deg)	θ (deg)	ϕ (deg)	Initial (dBi)	Final (dBi)	Radiated Power (dBi)	Inverse Axial Ratio	Tilt (deg)	Radiated Power (dBi)	Inverse Axial Ratio	Tilt (deg)
0	0	0	0	4.37	4.37	2.18	0.939	-45.1	2.18	0.939	-45.0
0	0	0	0	4.37	4.37	2.18	0.998	-78.6	2.18	1.000	-1.4
45	0	-45	0	1.16	1.95	1.83	0.237	-89.5	0.58	0.618	88.6
80	0	-80	0	-1.50	1.36	2.18	0.002	90.0	-0.75	0.133	89.5
20	45	-20	0	3.60	3.61	1.83	0.804	89.2	1.80	0.911	88.4
45	45	-45	0	1.00	1.55	1.25	0.310	89.5	0.58	0.618	88.6
60	45	-60	0	-0.81	0.67	1.19	0.102	89.7	-0.16	0.408	88.8
80	45	-80	0	-2.53	0.24	1.06	0.004	90.0	-0.75	0.133	89.5

Table 3. Transferred Power Using Two Pairs of Dipoles with Both Optimized.

Direction of Propagation Relative to the Transmit Pair		Direction of Propagation Relative to the Receive Pair		Power Transferred		Transmit Pair Final Parameters			Receive Pair Final Parameters		
θ (deg)	ϕ (deg)	θ (deg)	ϕ (deg)	Initial (dBi)	Final (dBi)	Radiated Power (dBi)	Inverse Axial Ratio	Tilt (deg)	Radiated Power (dBi)	Inverse Axial Ratio	Tilt (deg)
0	0	0	0	4.37	4.37	2.18	0.999	-45.0	2.18	1.000	-45.0
40	0	-40	0	1.70	4.37	2.18	0.000	-90.0	2.18	0.000	-90.0
80	0	-80	0	-1.50	4.37	2.18	0.000	90.0	2.18	0.000	90.0
70	45	0	45	0.06	0.85	0.77	0.031	83.8	2.18	0.138	45.3
70	90	0	0	0.41	4.37	2.18	0.000	90.0	2.18	0.000	-89.9
80	45	0	0	-1.35	3.25	1.06	0.000	90.0	2.18	0.003	-89.9

Finally, both transmit and receive dipole pairs were optimized. The results of several simulations where both dipoles were optimized are shown in Table 3. Note that in several cases the power transferred is the maximum possible for a pair of dipoles. For values of θ close to 0° the optimization tends towards an exact match of the polarization between transmit and receive antennas, and it is usually close to circular polarization. As the angle θ increases, the optimization changes to a linearly polarized wave. This is intuitive for $\phi = 0^\circ$ and $\phi = 90^\circ$ as the dipoles parallel to the direction of propagation tend to be turned off, and the power transferred is the same as if there were only a single dipole as both the transmitter and the receiver. This tendency towards linear polarization holds true for angles of $\phi = 45^\circ$, but both dipoles in the pair contribute part of the signal. The optimization also takes significantly longer for angles of $\phi = 45^\circ$ than other angles, because the best solution adjusts both the magnitude and the phase of the second dipole, where at the other angles of ϕ considered depend primarily on a magnitude adjustment.

In conclusion, optimizing of both transmit and receive antennas using pairs of crossed dipoles always increase the power transferred between the two. The optimization tends to use linear polarization at large angles of θ . The ability to optimize at both ends of a communication system may pose formidable challenges from a controls system standpoint, but the optimization at only one end using the transmitter dipole pair indicates that some improvement may be easily implemented on one end of a communication system. Additional simulations and an experimental setup would be in order to further understand the optimization's ability to increase power transferred between two pairs of crossed dipoles.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In general, the ability to generate the desired circular polarization with a pair of crossed dipoles was established using the selected optimization method. The objective function used the polarization sense, the axial ratio, and the

radiated power in a user-defined optimization direction by adjusting the amplitude and phase of one of the dipoles. Initially, this correction of the polarization eliminated the loss caused by the polarization loss factor. Although the optimization is almost always able to achieve the desired circular polarization in the optimization direction, the change in the radiated power in that same direction may offset or decrease the total gain. To overcome this effect, the optimization was changed to consider the transferred power for determining the efficiency of a solution.

For dipoles having a minimum separation, usually the loss of power in the direction of optimization causes a greater loss than the non-optimized setup. Similar results are found for the cases containing a ground plane, where the optimization does not improve the total gain, even though it does reduce the polarization loss.

The cases where the polarization optimization improves the total power occur when the spacing between the crossed dipoles is increased beyond 0.25 wavelength, but generally is not an improvement over a non-adaptive system.

The general failure of the polarization loss optimization prompted a revised optimization scheme based on the total power transferred. The results are promising for a dipole pair with minimum separation where the total power transferred is always increased by the optimization for angles of $\theta < 80^\circ$, with the largest gains occurring as θ increases, or as the non-optimize gain decreases. This revised optimization holds great promise as a method to increase the gain of a communication system using an amplitude and phase adjustment. This final setup also indicates that it is not beneficial to optimize to reduce the polarization loss, but an increase in the polarization loss yields an increase in transferred power in the direction of optimization.

The optimization for total power transferred was extended to consider pairs of crossed dipoles at each end of the communication system. When only the transmitter pair was

optimized, the additional directivity of the receiver increases the power transferred by up to 2.1 dB. The optimization of both the transmitter and the receiver antennas further improved the power transferred up to the limits of the dipoles.

Recommendations for Future Work

The first area of consideration might be a look at adjusting the phase or amplitude of the second dipole to attempt to increase the transferred power. From the results in this project it appears that when ϕ is about 45° the correction involves only a phase shift, and the correction when ϕ is 0° or 90° is mostly accomplished by adjusting the amplitude of the second dipole.

Second, an experimental setup would be in order to verify the simulations for this project. It would require a method of adjusting the amplitude and phase of one dipole and allowing the effectiveness of the solution to be measured in a desired direction. These controls and measurements would then need to be available to the computer system running the optimization algorithm. The results should be approximately the same as those found in the simulations done with this project.

Finally, it would also be interesting to investigate the possibility of adjusting the response of antennas with circular polarization, such as a helix. Further investigations in the ability of an optimization technique to adjust the response of such antennas would be in order. This optimization would attempt to increase the transferred power in a chosen optimization direction.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. E. Marshall and C. W. Bostian, "An adaptive polarization correction scheme using circular polarization," *IEEE International Antennas and Propagation Society Symposium, Atlanta, GA*, pp. 395-397, June 1974.
- [2] R. T. Compton, "On the performance of a polarization sensitive adaptive array," *IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation*, vol. AP-29, pp. 718-725, Sept. 1981.
- [3] G. J. Burke and A. J. Poggio, *Numerical Electromagnetics Code (NEC2) User's Manual*. Livermore, CA: Lawrence Livermore Lab., 1981.

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